

A Study of Some Fundamental Ethical Concepts in Philosophy

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Abstract

This paper attempts to solve the problem why do we need to know the fundamental concepts? (Research problem) The research finding is to know the future generation, the concepts are very important. (Research finding) We used the descriptive method and evaluative method. (Research method) Ethical principle is used to resolve the research problem. (Principle) These ethical concepts support in resolving the ethical conflicts that arise in life. (Contribution) If these concepts are clearly understand, any benefit outcome can be surely attained.

Key words : 1. Is and Ought 2. Absolute and Relative 3. Egoistic and Altruistic

Introduction

Ethics is a field of philosophy or one of the areas of study in philosophy. The English word "Ethics" comes from the Greek word "ethos". Ethics is systematic study of morals. The term 'moral' is derived from the Latin word 'moralis' which means 'customs' or 'mores' which essentially means 'character'. The aim of ethics is to determine moral aspect of human behaviour and showing what is worth striving for, what behaviour is good, what meaning to life.

Ethics is an axiological study for it critically studies and evaluates human conduct. It is also a normative study as it lays emphasis upon norms, standards and principles of human conducts.

Thus, Ethics is that study or discipline which concerns itself with judgements of approval and disapproval, judgements as to the rightness and wrongness, goodness or badness, virtue or vice, desirability or wisdom of actions, dispositions, ends, objects or states of affairs. Ethical judgements involve values and value judgements, as well as the sense of ought and sense of should for the good of humanity.

For mankind 'Ethics' is essential, for ethics is a normative science of the conduct of man. Man is a social being who cannot live a life of isolation. A human being has to live a with other like beings to live and flourish, living thus together and striving for one's personal well-being as well as those of others which thus led to the emergence of society, culture and civilization. The continuity and preservation of culture however depends largely on human knowledge and conduct, especially moral conduct.

Ethics seeks to define the moral ideas of particular cultures as well as to seek universal principles for mankind in general. It is concerned with the ideal or standard to with our conduct should conform. Ethics evaluates human conduct and examines its rightness and wrongness.

The function of Ethics is to lay down value judgements or criteria by which we may distinguish the 'good' from the 'bad' the 'right' from the 'wrong' the 'is' from the 'ought' and the 'can' from the 'cannot'. This is the most important function of philosophy.

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1. The Fundamental Ethical Concepts

The fundamental ethical concepts and norms are an important role in the study of ethics. We can generally study the ethical concepts are as follows: (1) The "Is" and The "Ought", (2) The "Absolute" and The "Relative", (3) The "Subjective" and The "Objective", (4) The "Formal" and The "Teleological", (5) The "Egoistic" and The "Altruistic", (6) The "Freedom" and The "Moral Responsibility".

The need to first clarify the ethical concepts and norms for without a clear understanding of these concepts efforts in applied ethics could very well lead to confusion and conflict. It is further necessary to note that life and the human condition is never at a standstill. But it is constantly changing. Especially today the world is changing as a fast and furious pace, so it would be prudent to try to understand the fundamental concepts of ethics and the differences in views that are important in the study of ethics before putting them to practice. It would be necessary to understand that in life which is constantly changing there are no absolutes but certain ethical principles and guide lines to provide help and support in resolving the ethical conflicts that arise in life.

1. 1. The "Is" and the "Ought"

The most fundamental concepts is the "Is" and the "Ought". The essence of the problem centres on the argument that "what ought to be" cannot be logically deduced from "what actually is". This question was raised by G.E. Moore and was named by him as the Naturalistic fallacy.

Whatever the case may be they belong to the field of "Is". The question is should we not try to change the "Is" to create better conditions of life? Contrary to Moore's argument some philosophers see no reason why the "Ought" cannot be deduced from the "Is". They maintain that historical records of the past can guide us as to what we should do for the future, and we can learn lessons from past events. This is known as the historical method. The "Ought" is concerned with standards, norms, criteria and so on.

Human beings have always endeavored to make life better, materially, socially, normally and spiritually through knowledge. The "Ought" has been realized by an evaluation of the "Is". Moral norms and judgements change as times change and the human intellect progresses, but it must not be claimed that such norms and judgements are universal and absolute truths that will never change, for there is always room for perfection. At the same time, it must be understood that there must be reasoned justifications for our moral beliefs and that some norms of moral behavior may vary from culture to culture and from time to time, there are some moral values and principles that are generally agreed upon and accepted by mankind as a whole whatever the difference in culture or religious creed. For human nature is basically the same in that human beings have the same capacity for evil and good.

Applied ethics used ethical principles as guidelines for living a good life. There is first the need to clarify the ethical concepts and norms, for without a clear understanding efforts in application could very well lead to confusion and conflict. It is further necessary to note that life and the human condition is never at a standstill but is in constant flux. Especially today the world is changing fast from day to day, so it would be prudent to try to understand the fundamental concepts of ethics and the differences in views that are characteristics of ethics before putting them to practice. Ethical principles and guidelines are agreed upon universally and they do provide help and support in resolving human difficulties and conflicts.

1. 2. The Absolute and the Relatives

The Absolute and the Relative is one of the important issues which need to be examined. The ethical relativist holds that there are no universal moral rules, ideas or standards that can justifiably be applied to people everywhere. Relativist holds that there exists great variation in the rules, ideas and standards accepted by different societies at different times in human history. Some say that not only societies but each individual has a right to determine what is right or wrong and that moral rules and values are all relative related to the time, space and circumstances. So, different societies have different moral values and moral rules or standards.

Moral relativist says that in ethics and morality there are no absolutes and that morality is relative to a specific culture, group or individuals. Greek philosopher Protagoras introduced the relativity of not only morality but also knowledge with his saying, "Man is the measure of all thing?" For the relativists, the moral beliefs of each person come from his own conscience or from his social environment. And most human beings are ethnocentric. They accepts, believes and generally adhere to the rules, ideas or standards of their own race society as the only ones that matter.

Absolutism maintains that moral criteria and moral values are universal and absolute. They maintain that there are moral codes which apply equally to all for all time and that changing circumstances make no difference. But as Immanuel kant pointed out a man may tell a lie but this man would never agree to a law that permits "lying" as a universal law; that everyone should be allowed to tell lies whenever he or she found it profitable or convenient. Absolutism is mostly advocated by those who subscribe to the deontological or formalistic view of ethics.

So, these two extreme views have become prominent in the twentieth century though they have been advocated by philosophers in ancient times. There are difficulties in both points of view, and it seems as though one point of view excludes the others. Jacques P. Thiroux in his "Ethics: Theory and Practice" point out that sometimes two norms or values that are considered absolute may conflict head-on, but he goes on to explain that they conflict because they are not genuine absolute truths. So, the question is "Are there absolute truths? Are all moral statements relative?" This problem of the opposition between the absolute and relative cannot be resolved on its own. We have to go further to reflect on what constitutes knowledge and to what extent human knowledge is said to be objective. This is an epistemological problem but it is a very important issue for ethics as well.

1. 3. The Subjective and the Objective

Objectivity of moral judgements and the consequent unity of morality has been discussed from the earliest stage of ethical theorizing. Protogoras and his sophists followers felt that "Man is the measure of all things". For them moral judgements are neither universal nor absolute. They are subjective.

Subjectivist ethics holds that moral judgements do not express anything universal and objective beyond human opinion. To declare an action right or wrong, a thing or a situation as good or bad, is merely to declare human likes and dislikes approvals and disapprovals, desire and interests etc. There is nothing involved. Moral judgements are conditioned by human subjective states. There are no unconditional moral judgements.

Some philosophers hold that morality is objective as moral values and moral norms. The term objective is ambiguous. In one sense it means its reality or existence. It exists by

itself. In other sense it means that which is universally accepted. The universal acceptance may be interpreted that if the conditions and circumstances are the same, the same action character or situation will have the same value. Moral judgements express something independent of the human mind.

In the issues of the subjective and the objective we should also reflect upon what Socrates said that "knowledge is virtue" and that the "Unexamined life is not worth living". In Buddhist ethics also wrongdoing is due to ignorance. If this point of view is accepted it would not be wrong to say that morality is subjective. But an act in itself may be considered morally objective. Killing, stealing, lying etc are all immoral irrespective of who commits it. Thus from this aspect moral norms and values may be considered objective.

1. 4. The Formal and the Teleological

Teleological and Deontological ethics has occupied the interest of philosophers for many years. Deontological ethics is also known as formalist ethics and its most outstanding exponent is Immanuel Kant. Formalist theories are based on the premise that moral behaviour is not determined by the consequences. That is acts or people are to be judged moral or immoral regardless of the consequences.

The consequentialist theory on the other hand maintains that human being ought to behave in ways that will bring about good consequences.

For the formalist, the standard of conduct is found in moral rules which are inherently right or wrong quite apart from any particular results which flow from them. Moral values are inherent in certain type of acts which follow fixed principles. It means that certain acts are moral by their very nature.

Formalists do not believe that the rightness or wrongness of an action depends upon the result of the action although they do believe that good results ordinarily follow from good actions and evil results from evil actions. Right and wrong are inherent in the nature of things.

Immanuel Kant is the outstanding representative of the view that actions are right or wrong according to their intrinsic nature, apart from any ends outside themselves. For Kant, a good motive or a good will is central. While there are many things which men consider good, but a good motive or good will is the only thing that has intrinsic value. Goodness is to be found in an inner quality of will motive or attitude and not in an outward performance or the consequences of one's act.

The teleological view of morality is in contrast to formalism. Teleological theories judge conduct as right or wrong in relation to some end or goal that is considered good. An action is considered right if it leads to good consequences. On the other hand, an action is considered wrong if it produces bad consequences. Hedonism, which is a teleological theory, holds that pleasure or happiness is the chief good in life. This doctrine emphasizes pleasure or happiness as the goal in life. It holds that pleasure alone is good.

Most human behavior is motivated by the will and emotions and desires. In certain cases the will or motive is good and in others there may be ill will. Kant and the formalists hold that if one does something out of ill will then even if it brings about unexpected good results then that act is immoral whereas those like Bentham and Mill who advocate teleological ethics holds that if any act brings about good results then it is a good and moral act irrespective of the will or intention behind it. For Consequentialists motives are unimportant and what-count are the results. They say that people's motives cannot be seen or measured but the consequences of their actions can, so only consequences should be considered.

1. 5. The Egoism and the Altruism

Ethical egoism is frequently enquired into in the field of moral theory. In Western tradition, the dichotomy between acting out of own self- interest and acting for the benefit of others has been marked by the terms egoism and altruism. Egoism is acting out of self- interest. Altruism is acting for the good of others. In Western philosophy there are various kinds of egoism, namely psychological egoism, descriptive egoism, rational egoism, ethical egoism, normative egoism and conditional egoism.

Ethical egoism is the normative theory that the promotion of one's own is in accordance with morality. In the strong version, it is held that it is always moral to promote one's own good. In the weak version, it is said that it is always moral to promote one's own good, it is not necessarily moral. There are conditions in which the avoidance of personal interest may be a moral action.

Ethical egoism is generally classified into three forms. The first form is concerned with the individual. "Everyone should or ought to act in self- interest." The second form is concerned with the personal. "I ought to act in my own self- interest; I make no claims about what others ought to do." The third form is concerned with the universal. "Everyone ought to act in his or her own self- interest,"

Altruism is the performance of duties to others without any sort of personal gain for one's efforts. If one performs an act beneficial to others with a view to gaining affection, respect, reputation, or any form of gratitude or remuneration then it is not an altruistic act. It is in fact a selfish act because the principal motivation was to reap some benefit for oneself. The desire of this benefit exists equally whether it is psychological emotional, intellectual, or material each form of desirable benefit is philosophically identical as a motivation. Altruism is unselfish concern for the welfare of others. It is a traditional virtue in many cultures, and a core aspect of various religious traditions.

Egoism is working for self and altruism is working for others. Human beings cannot survive alone but live with others of like nature for welfare and survival. Both egoism and altruism taken to extremes would make life impractical. Human beings have to live with others to survive and flourish are obliged to carry out certain duties and obligations.

1. 6. Freedom and Moral Responsibility

Freedom and Determinism is also very important in the study of ethics. Freedom is crucial because it is related to whether human beings can be held morally responsible for what they do. Determinism means that every event caused, and effect or event a cause or causes and conditions exist. Those who advocate the deterministic view hold that there is no such thing as an uncaused result, effect or event and human being themselves are determined by forces beyond their control.

The kind of determinism holds that everything that happens is caused and is beyond human control is called hard determinism in contrast to soft determinism. Which hold that everything is caused but does not go to the extent of saying it is beyond human control. Hard determinism essentially maintains that if all events are caused then there can be no such thing as freedom or freewill.

The various forms of determinism including fatalism deny freedom or free will and this controversy has powerful implications for morality and moral responsibility. But first it would be necessary to fist clarity what freedom means. It is argued that it morality is to be sound, human beings must have free will, that is, they must have the freedom to choose to do good or

bad and right or wrong. Those who advocate free will are often also called Indeterminists and their views as Indeterminism. Indeterminism believes that utmost freedom can be found in the area of human reflection and choice especially moral reflection and decision making.

William James (1842-1910) is the most prominent exponent of this view. James holds that to strive to be good and to feel regret over wrong done are indications of freedom. Human beings have always made efforts to improve life since ancient times. They may make mistakes due to the decisions they make shows that they make decisions of their own free will.

The only way out of this dilemma is to maintain that though human freedom may be limited and there are times when actions are beyond human control as for instance when a human being is forced to do something wrong at gunpoint, it cannot be denied that to a certain extent each individual is free to desire or not desire, to choose or not be choose and to act or not to act and to that extent a human being has moral responsibility.

Conclusion

Any person who has concern for culture and civilization will concern himself with practical and ethical issues, for ethics has to do with human conduct. The need for ethics arises from the fact that man is not perfect by nature: he has to train himself to be good. Thus morality becomes the most important aspect of living. Morality is an observance of the laws of wholesome living.

"Study of Mankind is Man" it is said. to study mankind 'Ethics' is essential, for Ethics is a normative science of the conduct of man. Man is a social being for he cannot lead a life alone. He cannot be separated from the community and he exchanges his notions of right and wrong, good and evil from the customs and manners established in his society. So the individual and the society are interdependent. Their individual dealing shall be in harmony for the sake of the common good or the social good.

Ethics is concerned with the "ought" and not the "is". Generally concerns with individual and what he ought to do to live a good and fruitful life in this world. Ethics critically estimates the moral rules and codes currently in practice. So, Ethics is a requirement for human life. It is our means of deciding a course of action, for better or wrose. Without it, our actions would be random and aimless. Therefore the role of ethics becomes essential mainly with the conduct of the individual.

We have to acknowledge that human society needs moral principles that would guide individuals to know right from wrong, good from evil. Thus morality becomes the most important aspect of living. Ethics critically studies the rules of good conduct. Moreover it is interested in how man ought to behave in order to live a good life. It lays down the students or criteria by which we can judge good conducts.

Reference

- Kar, K. N. (1950). *Ethics*. Yangon: Sapay Beikman Press.
- Lillie, Williom. (1948). *An Introduction of Ethics*. New York: Methuen and Noble Inc.
- Melden, A. J. (1955). *Ethical Theories*. Prentice- hall Inc.
- Thiroux, Jacques P. (1980). *Ethics: Theory and Practice*. New York: Macmillan Publishing.
- Titus, H. H. (1966). *Ethics for Today*. New Delhi: Eurasia Publishing House.